

Evolution of temperature-attributable mortality trends looking at social inequalities: an observational case study of urban maladaptation to cold and heat

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ABSTRACT

Background To date, little is known about the temporal variation of the temperature-mortality association among different demographic and socio-economic groups. The aim of this work is to investigate trends in cold- and heat-attributable mortality risk and burden by sex, age, education, marital status, and household occupancy in the city of Turin, Italy.

Methods We collected daily time-series of temperature and mortality counts by demographic and socio-economic groups for the period 1982-2018 in Turin. We applied standard quasi-Poisson regression models to data subsets of 25-year moving subperiods, and we estimated the temperature-mortality associations with distributed lag non-linear models (DLNM). We provided cross-linkages between the evolution of minimum mortality temperatures, relative risks of mortality and temperature-attributable deaths under cold and hot conditions.

Results Our findings highlighted an overall increase in risk trends under cold and heat conditions. All-cause mortality at the 1st percentile increased from 1.15 (95% CI: 1.04; 1.28) in 1982-2006 to 1.24 (95% CI: 1.11; 1.38) in 1994-2018, while at the 99th percentile the risk shifted from 1.51 (95% CI: 1.41; 1.61) to 1.59 (95% CI: 1.49; 1.71). In relation to social differences, women were characterized by greater values in respect to men, and similar estimates were observed among the elderly in respect to the youngest subgroup. Risk trends by educational subgroups were mixed, according to the reference temperature condition. Finally, individuals living in conditions of isolation were characterized by higher risks, with an increasing vulnerability throughout time.

Conclusions The overall increase in cold- and heat-related mortality risk suggests a maladaptation to ambient temperatures in Turin. Despite alert systems in place increase public awareness and improve the efficiency of existing health services at the local level, they do not necessarily prevent risks in a homogeneous way. Targeted public health responses to cold and heat in Turin are urgently needed to adapt to extreme temperatures due to climate change.

Keywords climate change; Italy; maladaptation; social inequalities; temperature; urban

List of abbreviations

AF, attributable fraction; CI, confidence intervals; DLNM, distributed lag nonlinear model; MMT, minimum mortality temperatures; RR, relative risk.

1. INTRODUCTION

The changing health risks under the influence of temperature variations, driven by human-induced climate change, by urbanization growth as well as by the influence of social determinants of health are known to be a major concern - among others - for public health policy makers and scientists (1). In fact, as global warming has become more evident, negative health impacts linked to the increase in the frequency, intensity and duration of extreme weather events are exacerbating human health conditions, bringing to a general rise in mortality and morbidity (2). By 2050, at 1.5°C of global warming, the population exposed to deadly heat in the world's most populous cities is estimated to be around 350 million, considering a midrange population growth scenario (3). The strongest extreme hot temperatures are projected to occur within Mediterranean region (2,4). In this context, Italy holds the uppermost heat-related effects on daily mortality considering hot temperatures (5). In fact, in the country, in particular near by the Alpine regions, it is expected an increase of temperatures up to 2°C in the period 2021-2050 and up to 5°C by 2100 (compared to 1981-2010) under the RCP 8.5 scenario (6). At the present, Italian citizens are more sensitive to uncomfortable conditions due to extreme events compared to other countries (7). Nonetheless, there are spatial differences between and within Italian urban areas (8) due to physical variables (such as urban land cover) (9) as well as the spatial distribution of social inequalities (10). It is well-established that the health risks related to temperatures depend on pure adaptation processes - such as individual behavioural changes and acclimatisation, but also on non-climate factors - such as the built

environment, population characteristics and the available health care services (11). An adequate distinction between these drivers of change is crucial to plan effective policies to address public health challenges related to heat- and cold- temperatures impacts at the urban scale (12). A comprehensive risk assessment requires detailed analyses with respect to potential changes in population susceptibility over time, considering the full temperature range, from cold to heat (13). In fact, despite it is undeniable that a growing risk to health is due to heat under climate change (1), it is unquestionable how cold events are responsible for a significant higher proportion of the overall health burden associated to temperatures (2,11). Disentangling the temporal changes of the risks under a complete range of temperatures can provide a more complete description of the evolution of the contribution of different adaptive mechanisms driven by: (i) non-climate factors such as socioeconomic development (i.e., extrinsic adaptation) (14,15), or (ii) physiological acclimatisation in response to changing temperatures (i.e., intrinsic adaptation) (16).

To date, despite several studies have already mentioned how the health effects of cold often exceed those of heat (17,18), cold-mortality associations over time have been poorly studied, showing controversial results (2,19). Over the years, a growing number of studies tried to assess the temporal variation in population vulnerability (10,13), expressed as minimum mortality temperatures (MMTs), relative risks (RRs) and attributable fraction (AFs). For example, in Spain, evidence of a reduction in mortality from respiratory and cardiovascular diseases have been found during the coldest and hottest months of the year (1980-2016)(16,20). Results from a multi-country study over the period 1985-2012 revealed an increase in population vulnerability under cold temperatures in Japan and South Korea, with a decline of RRs under hotter conditions. Similar trends were observed for the US (21). In Sweden, an increase in MMTs over the course of the 20th century, suggested an adaptation pattern to increasing temperatures (15), as found similarly by Hajat et al. (22) in the UK. Understanding the evolution of MMT, RR and AF, it is necessary to support health policymakers in the comprehension of the potential drivers of change, managing and preventing risks from the temperature-related health nexus under present and climate change scenario conditions (11). Therefore, adequate public health planning in urban areas should be based on quantitative evaluation – such as the one provided in this study – to prevent cold- and heat- mortality and morbidity (13,19,23). The present paper assesses the temporal changes in temperature-mortality associations by sex, age, education, marital status, and household's occupancy in the city of Turin, Italy. In doing so, the study provides cross-linkages between the evolution of MMT, RR of mortality and temperature-AF of death under a broad range of temperatures along the whole year period.

2. METHODS

2.1 Data sources

We collected daily time series of mortality counts and temperatures from the 1st of January 1982 to the 31st of December 2018 in the city of Turin, the biggest urban area in the northwest of Italy. The Regional Epidemiology Unit of the local health authority (ASL TO3) provided daily mortality data from all causes, disaggregated by sex, age, education, marital status, and number of household occupants (24). Daily mean temperature was selected as the main exposure variable (25).

High-resolution gridded data (~5.5 km) was derived from the UERRA Regional reanalysis Dataset (26), and the daily time-series was generated by computing a median value of all grid points located within the city boundaries. Both mortality and temperature datasets had no missing values. These data have been used and described in a previous analysis (27).

2.2 Statistical analysis

First, we performed a time-series generalized linear model with standard quasi- Poisson regression to derive estimates of temperature-mortality associations by population subgroups and data subsets of 25-year moving periods, summarised as RR values. The sub-periods analysed were 1982-2006, 1983-2007, and so forth, up until 1994-2018. In accordance with previous studies (16,28), the former model included a natural cubic spline of time with 8 degrees of freedom (df) per year to control for seasonality and long-term trend. The day-of-the-week (dow) factor was finally inserted in the time series quasi-Poisson regression as an indicator variable. Then, to investigate the complex non-linear dependency and the delayed effect between extreme temperatures and mortality on the scale of lag, a distributed lag non-linear model (DLNM) was included through the definition of a cross-basis function, obtained by the combination of two functions describing respectively the exposure-response association and the lag-response association for a given interval (29). More specifically, the exposure-response curve was modelled consisting of a natural cubic B-spline with three internal knots placed at the 10th, 75th and 90th percentile of the temperature distribution (16,30,31). On the other hand, the temporal effect of daily extreme temperatures on mortality was taken into account by the lag-response function, which was based on a natural cubic spline with an intercept and three internal knots placed at equally spaced values in the log scale (32). To capture the potential short-term harvesting (heat) as well as the long-lagged associations (cold), we extended the lag period up to 21 days (20,31). These modelling choices were thoroughly tested in sensitivity analyses by varying the modelling choices (i.e., time-varying DLNM or 15-, 20-, 25-years moving period) as well as the modelling assumptions to apply (i.e., number of knots to include, the degrees of freedom to consider and, finally, the number of lags to examine). In fact, for the evaluation and comparison of the statistical models to be implemented, we used the quasi-Akaike criteria (qAIC), which provides a measure of the quality of the estimation of a statistical model by considering both the goodness of fit and the complexity of the model (29,33). Therefore, based on the qAIC, we chose the model which furnished the lowest score compared to other choices.

The temperature-mortality RR curves obtained in each of the 13 subperiods of 25 consecutive years were centred at the MMT of the specific subperiod - which is the temperature at which the RR of death is at its minimum or lowest value - and used to compute the mortality burden (i.e., AF) attributable to temperatures during the all-year period. These analyses have been developed to understand the AF changes over time during the hottest (i.e., June-August) and the coldest (i.e., December-February) months of the year. This MMT values was calculated with its confidence intervals (95% CI) by a parametric bootstrap method proposed in previous studies (27,31). Moreover, to estimate the mortality burden attributable to the different months across the whole study period, here reported as relative excess (i.e., attributable fraction of mortality), we used a method described in Gasparrini and Leone (34). Finally, the statistical significance of the RR trends by subgroup was estimated with a linear regression model by running 1000 Monte Carlo simulations, based on the normal approximation of the RRs.

R software (version 4.0.3) was utilised to create data sets and to develop statistical models and outputs using functions from *splines* and *dlnm* packages.

Figure 1 | Evolution of annual mean temperatures for (a) all, (b) summer, and (c) winter months, 1982–2018
 Summer is represented by the hottest months of the year (June, July, and August) and winter is represented by the coldest months of the year (December, January, and February). The anomalies reflect the difference relative to the average of the 1982-2011 period in Turin (Italy).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Evolution of mortality and temperatures in Turin

The dataset included 364,755 deaths covering a period of 37 years, from the 1st January 1982 to the 31st December 2018. Analyses and results here presented were stratified by sex (“women” [51.4%] and “men” [48.6%]), age (“65-84 years” [51.62%] and “equal or over 84 years” [31.18%]), education (“until primary school” [56.9%] and “over primary school” [37.49%]), marital status (“married” [47.94%], “unmarried” [15.82%] and “widower” [31.06%]) and number of household occupants (“alone” [29.58%] and “not alone” [64.58%]). Analyses by individuals younger than 65 years were not computed, because of the small number of daily deaths counts recorded for those age ranges, which did not guarantee model convergence and optimal fitting. Overall, the evolution of all mortality and number of deaths by sex over time remained more or less constant over the study period (see Fig.A.1 in Appendix). In relation to the age, the two subgroups displayed opposite trends of mortality. The “65-84 years” visibly decreased, while the “over 84 years” increased over time. Fig.1 shows the evolution of annual, summer (JJA) and winter (DJF) mean temperature anomalies over the period 1982-2018. As expected, these temperatures have been increasing, on average, at a rate of 0.26°C, 0.16°C and 0.43°C per decade, respectively.

3.2 Trends in the minimum mortality temperature and in the risk of death

The temporal evolution of MMTs by population subgroups and subperiods is provided in Fig.2 (with MMT Confidence Intervals visible in the Supplementary Fig.B.1, section B in the Appendix). Overall, the MMT trends highlighted an increase for all the sub-groups under analysis, except for the over-aged subgroup which corresponded to the oldest and the widowed, where the MMTs values remain relatively stable. More specifically, in relation to “all-causes mortality”, MMT evolution increased over the 13 sub-periods (by 0.5°C from 1982 to 2018); increase correlated with the rise in mean temperatures observed for the same period. Between the 1990-2014 and the 1994-2018, MMT values progressively increased in “women” and “men”, with a more visible increased tendency for women. In fact, the “men” pooled overall MMT corresponded to 22.5°C in 1982 and 2018, while in

“women” the MMT values increased from 21.3°C to 22.4°C. When considering age, results differed. Specifically, MMTs initially declined for the “65-84 years” subgroup and then considerably increased towards the end of the period, while for “over 84 years” remained rather stable. In the case of education, MMTs evolution for the "until-primary school" increased over time from 22.1°C in 1982 to 22.4°C in 2018, whereas for the "over-primary school", MMT values increased with a significant shift from 21.6°C in the 1986-2010 subperiod to 22.4°C in 1987-2011. Within the marital status category, MMTs were generally higher for the “married” and “widower” subgroups. Specifically, in the case of “married”, MMTs evolution increased from 22.3°C to 22.7°C, while for the “widower” remained around 22.4°C for the whole period. The “unmarried” subgroup - although some visible fluctuations – was the one with the most visible increasing trend, from 18.1°C in 1982-06 to 21.9°C in 2006-18. Finally, in relation to the household occupancy group, MMTs increased significantly both for the “alone” (from 21.7°C to 22.4°C) and for the “not alone” (from 22.2°C to 22.5°C).

Figure 2 | Minimum mortality temperature (°C) by subgroup

MMT = Minimum Mortality Temperature

RR estimates were extracted from the RR curves computed from the 13 subperiods of 25 consecutive years, which are provided in Fig.3, for the 1982-2006 (initial) and the 1994-2018 (final)

subperiod.

Figure 3 | Overall cumulative temperature-mortality relationships by subgroup, 1982-2006 vs 1994-2018
1982-2006 in blue and 1994-2018 in red

Pooled overall RR estimates indicated that both cold- and hot- temperatures were associated with a general increased risks in mortality, looking at the most extreme temperature percentiles. Overall, the slope of the RR curves under hotter conditions was steeper than under the colder ones, with values varied consistently by subgroups. In fact, RR values associated with the temperature-mortality relationships by all-causes, sex, education, and dwelling's occupants group revealed an increased risk of mortality over subperiods, under both cold and hot conditions. While, in relation to age and marital status, this trend was not so consistent among subgroups. By looking at age, for example, while the youngest revealed a slight increase of risks over subperiods, the oldest indicated the opposite (albeit with minor changes). Besides, the heat-related risk curve was much steeper than the cold-related ones, with a wider slope for women, the oldest, and people under more isolated conditions. In particular, the RR at the 1st percentile increased from 1.15 (95% CI: 1.04; 1.28) in 1982-2006 to 1.24 (95% CI: 1.11; 1.38) in 1994-2018 for "all-causes mortality", from 1.11 (95% CI: 0.96; 1.29) to 1.23 (95% CI: 1.05; 1.43) in "men", and from 1.19 (95% CI: 1.03; 1.37) to 1.25 (95% CI: 1.08; 1.44) "in women". In parallel, for the 99th percentile, the RR increased from 1.51 (95% CI: 1.41; 1.61) to 1.59 (95% CI: 1.49; 1.71), from 1.34 (95% CI: 1.27; 1.47) to 1.45 (95% CI: 1.31; 1.60), and from 1.68 (95% CI: 1.54; 1.84) to 1.74 (95% CI: 1.58; 1.91) respectively. RR curve for "65-84 years" in the 1994-2018 sub-period highlighted a slight and steady growth under both cold and hot conditions over subperiods. On the contrary, the "over 84 years" exhibited a slight decrease in RR values under both cold and hot conditions, with a change from 1.39 (95% CI: 1.26; 1.71) to 1.35 (95% CI: 1.14; 1.61) at the 1st percentile and from 1.83 (95% CI: 1.62; 2.08) to 1.78 (95% CI: 1.60; 2.00) at the 99th percentile. In relation to education, RR curves highlighted an increase under cold and hot conditions with an increased RRs from 1.18 (95% CI: 1.03; 1.34) to 1.26 (95% CI: 1.09; 1.45) at the 1st percentile for the "until primary school", and from 1.09 (95% CI: 0.91; 1.30) to 1.23 (95% CI: 1.05; 1.45) for the "over primary school". In parallel, the RR at the 99th percentile increased from 1.55 (95% CI: 1.43; 1.69) to 1.57 (95% CI: 1.43; 1.73) in the less educated subgroup, and from 1.40 (95% CI: 1.25; 1.56) to 1.59 (95% CI: 1.43; 1.76) in the most educated ones. Within the marital status category, similar RR trends have been observed, apart from the "unmarried" subgroup which showed a different trend, probably because the model did not adequately converge for the limited amount of observations. RRs showed more positive and significant curves and estimates for the "unmarried" and "widower" subgroups, despite the "married" ones. Finally, in relation to RRs estimates for the household occupants group, increased RR trends have been found in respect to the "alone" and the "not alone" subgroups. In fact, the RR at the 1st percentile slightly increased from 1.22 (95% CI: 1.00; 1.47) to 1.25 (95% CI: 1.04; 1.45) in the first subgroup, and from 1.11 (95% CI: 0.97; 1.26) to 1.25 (95% CI: 1.09; 1.42) in the second. Under the 99th percentile, RRs increased from 1.53 (95% CI: 1.36; 1.73) to 1.66 (95% CI: 1.48; 1.87) and from 1.48 (95% CI: 1.36; 1.60) to 1.53 (95% CI: 1.40; 1.67) respectively.

To illustrate more specifically the trends over each of the 13 analysed subperiods, Fig.4 shows the RRs evolution at the 1st and at the 99th temperature percentiles, with 95% empirical confidence intervals (CI) (Supplementary Table C.1 in the Appendix provides RR estimates and 95% CI by subgroups and subperiods). In general, RR trends resulted to be statistically significant for each subgroup under analysis (more details within Supplementary Table C.2 in the Appendix, section C).

Figure 4 | Temporal evolution of relative risk by subgroup by 25-years subperiods
 1st percentile in blue and 99th percentile of temperatures in red

3.3 Monthly attributable mortality: focus on cold- and heat- AF

Fig.5 summarizes the evolution of the AF by months and by subgroups between the first and the last subperiods. The overall trend highlighted AF differences between the coldest (“Dec”, “Jan” and “Feb”) and the hottest months (“Jun”, “Jul” and “Aug”) of the year, here defined as cold- and heat-AF. In agreement with previous findings, results revealed (apart from few specific cases) a general increase in AFs from 1982-2006 to 1994-2018, with more visible rises in cold-AFs and a less noticeable increase in heat-AFs (see Supplementary Table C.3 in the Appendix for more details). This is the case for “all-causes mortality”, “men”, “65-84 years”, “until-” and “over-” “primary school”, “married” and “unmarried” subgroups, and – finally – the “alone” and the “not alone”. On contrary, “women” revealed very similar cold- and heat- AFs between subperiods, which assumed a stable trend under the most extreme percentile of temperatures. In the “over 85 years” subgroup, cold-AFs of the initial period exceeded the ones corresponded to the last one, implying a slight adaptation of this category to cold temperatures over time. Finally, in the case of “widower”, it emerged a decrease of cold-AFs and an increase of heat-AFs.

Multiple sensitivity analyses were performed using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to identify the most explicative model to use and the appropriate parameters to adopt, with the aim to capture

the main effects related to cold- and heat- events. All sensitivity examinations suggested that the reported results were not dependent on modelling choices (i.e., time-varying DLNM or 15-, 20-, 25-years moving period) (see Supplementary Fig.D.1 and D.2 in the Appendix) and on modelling assumption (i.e., knots, degrees of freedom and lag-period) (see Supplementary Fig.D.3 and D.4 in the Appendix). Please, note that, since the RR curves are centred at different MMT values in each subperiod, the RR and AF values are not perfectly comparable between the different subperiods.

Figure 5 – Evolution of monthly attributable fraction of mortality by subgroup, 1982-2006 vs 1994-2018
1982-2006 in blue and 1994-2018 in red

4. DISCUSSION

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study in which the evolution of the impacts of temperature on mortality is investigated among population categorized by sex, age, education, marital status, and household's occupants. Results of this investigation contributes to comprehensively understand the overall temperature-mortality trends within an urban context, reporting evolution of risks in relation to social inequalities across the last decades, under cold and hot conditions. And, although results from a singular study cannot be generalised to other locations, this research allowed us to provide a more specific overview on how different drivers affect the temperature-mortality relationships within cities, and how these drivers can be crosslinked between each other. Results suggested that the effects of cold and heat varied differently by subperiods and subgroups. In fact, our analysis demonstrated how - despite the considered subperiod - women are characterized by greater risks under hot and cold conditions in respect to men. A similar consideration can be derived for the elderly in respect to the youngest subgroup considered within the study, who, however, demonstrated a light decreasing trend in risks. This result may also relate to the fact that most of the population over the age of 85 is composed by women, who in Italy have a longer life expectancy. More difficult to interpret are the risk trends related to education, since - despite the increasing risk – the more educated were found to be more vulnerable under hot conditions, while those less educated were more vulnerable under cold temperatures. Finally, as previously found in another study conducted by the authors (27), individuals living in conditions of isolation (e.g., widowers) were characterized by higher risks, with an increasing vulnerability throughout time. Moreover, as expected, cross-linkages between groups were visible. In fact, the profile of women, the elderly, the less educated, and the most isolated shared more similarities between them than the others subgroups, probably due to the fact that aging is very feminine in Italy as well as in Europe (10,24). In this regard, since the death records referred to the past decades, it is reasonable to assume that women have been generally characterized by lower level of education and higher level of isolation, given the more advanced age at which they died. Contrary to the existing literature (14,19), our analyses showed a general increase in the risks due to cold and hot conditions, findings which have substantial implications for climate change health adaptation policies.

In the analyses, MMTs increased in parallel with the rise in mean temperature along the study period, for all the subgroups. This warming is consistent with findings of previous studies across Europe (15,16,35). For instance, in Spain the overall MMT increased by 0.7°C from the 1980-94 to the 2002-16 subperiods (16), while in France it increased by 0.4°C in winter and by 0.6°C in

summer between the 1982-95 and the 1996-2009 subperiods (35). While some of these studies support the hypothesis that increased MMT is concomitant with increased temperatures through human adaptation over time (15,35), our analyses demonstrated what was expressed by Achebak et al. (16). In particular, the simultaneous timing of increases in MMTs and mean temperatures, suggested that the temporal evolution of risks (and therefore of AFs) is closely associated to changes in the shape and slopes of exposure-response curves, instead of on MMTs evolutions and temperature warming.

Results on RRs and AFs under hot temperatures, revealed an increasing trend that has not been found in other investigations over Italian urban areas (14,36). These could be attributed to the fact that the periods under analysis were different and there was not such temporal continuity in these studies. In parallel, results related to cold temperatures highlighted also an increasing trend, confirming the theory by which “countries with mildest winter climates exhibit the highest variations in seasonal cold mortality” (28,38). Based on these findings, two considerations necessitate further explanations. Firstly, the maladaptation to heat might be attributed to the fact that approximately half of Turin residents born in the south of Italy and immigrated in the city during the 1950s/1960s (24). By origin, this population was genetically and phenotypically more heat-adapted than the natives, due to more extreme heat conditions in the South of the peninsula. Over time, due to the acclimation processes, there may have been a loss of this resilience against heat for these population groups. Inversely for cold, the rationale is not so intuitive. Secondly, Turin - like many cities in other European regions - has a low proportion of institutionalized elderly, due to a lack of supply on the one hand (e.g., long waiting lists), and to a cultural attitude towards home care of the elderly from family members on the other (24). This may have been especially impactful in relation to heat, since the health care residences were all air conditioned only after the 2003 heat wave.

Mortality risks by sex revealed an enhanced vulnerability over time to heat for women, while risk trends due to cold were similar among the two sex subgroups. To date, many studies confirmed how risks and AF due to heat is often higher in women (10,16), while risks due to cold is generally higher in men (20,39). This heterogeneity within sex subgroups might be related to socio-economic, cultural and health factors (16), which can differ between women and men, but also between age classes (20). In fact, in relation to age, we observed a decrease in vulnerability to heat in the oldest group, which is often the most vulnerable to extreme temperature conditions (27). However, this decrease in risk was not observed in individuals aged 65 to 85 years. Findings on previous studies by age differences were mixed (13,40). In accordance with these analyses, a decrease in AFs have been found in de’Donato et al. (40) for the 85+ age group under hot conditions, while Almendra et al. (19) highlighted higher cold-related mortality for the elderly, trend which increased with ageing. In this context, several aspects need further explanations. First, in 37 years of time series the change of birth generations is a critical point. Thanks to more advantageous living conditions, the entry into old age of new post-II war baby boomers led to a steady increase in the longevity of Turin's elderly (24). Nevertheless, this aspect will be more visible in individuals who are now around 65-84 years. Secondly, a flow that could influence the risk trends over the last subperiods could be attributable to the enlargement of the first post-I war baby boomers, which nowadays are over-90s (24). Another important phenomenon is the “frailty bias”: premature mortality (i.e., under 70 years) reaps the frailest in some vulnerable categories, while letting them survive in more advantaged social categories (41). This could cause the less educated and lonely to be more resilient, since the frailest

have been already subjected to premature mortality. Therefore, as a consequence, the strongest ones survived (42). In support of this reasoning, our results highlighted higher RRs for subgroup characterized by lower education, with a stronger increase for the most educated under hot conditions. Similar RR values and trends have been observed for the “most isolated”, which exhibited an increase of vulnerability over the years. In this context, a low income (indirectly related to single person salary/pension) (43) together with the stress due to loneliness may contribute to degrade even more the state of health (44,45). In contrast, different trends have been observed under cold, which highlighted a decreasing trend in RR especially from the central subperiods onwards. About relatively warm countries, literature explained how the elderly often fail to wear protective clothing and often do not remain indoors (46), which implies a lack of knowledge and awareness of safe temperatures (47). This could bring this population to be more exposed to cold weather conditions. But, over the years, the school reform in Italy seems to have improved the average level of education, while also providing more opportunities for the most vulnerable groups (24). This may have increased the level of education of the elderly population as well as the degree of awareness, resulting in a decreasing trend under cold temperatures.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time in which cold- and heat- trends in sex, age, education, marital status, and household occupants have been analysed within a Southern European urban context.

4.1 Strength and limitations of this work

Through the application of a flexible modelling framework which estimated the cold- and heat-mortality associations over time, our study provided an original contribution able to capture the evolution of mortality under extreme percentile of temperatures within an Italian urban context over the last decades. In the state-of-the-art literature, most analyses compare the absolute number of deaths occurring during heatwave or cold-spell events (48) or estimate aggregated RRs and/or AFs at an aggregate level, aspect which might mask within-country/urban trends (11,49). In this sense, results from a single city case study cannot be generalised to other locations since the relationship between social inequalities and the heat-health nexus vary by context, but the methodology to reach them could be replicated and, at the same time, the achieved findings could support policymakers in understanding how these temperature impacts can evolve within different population subgroups. Further, to our knowledge, our study covers the longest period in which changes in education, marital status, and household occupants have been investigated. However, some limitations must be acknowledged. Despite the importance of seasonal influenza and air pollution – which could affect the estimates on effects of cold on population susceptibility - we did not disentangle these confounding factors due to the lack of data. Nevertheless, these factors should not confound the outcomes of these analysis since the aim was related to the long-term trend that is not collinear with any known phenomenon of change in the prevalence of influenza infections between years. Moreover, their confounding role is currently under debate in research (11,19,22). In addition, we did not include the causes of death due to the limitation of available years during the study. Finally, the inclusion of urban design parameters as well as the evaluations of specific adaptive measures to recommend based on these results (such as the use of heating and cooling systems, the greenery of a city or priority actions depending on the most deprived neighbourhoods), which could contribute to mitigate the risks under heat- and cold- conditions, were not considered. Notwithstanding, subsequent comprehensive spatiotemporal analyses, inclusive of all these aspects (i.e.,

climate-urban health-inequalities elements) are under development in a further dedicated scientific study.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Understanding how urban populations have adapted locally to cold and heat in each specific urban context in the last decades, is important for determining future city planning. In this context, findings from our study indicated that although extreme temperature events are arising in Turin, increases of mortality due to both cold- and heat- temperatures has been observed over the last decades. After the 2003 heat wave in Europe, it has been shown that health consequences may be avoided or partly reduced through the activation of local alarm systems, such as national heat plans (14,52) or winter seasonal health plans (51,52). Although these alert systems increase public awareness and improve the efficiency of existing health services, they do not necessarily prevent risks in a homogeneous way (23,48). Adequate public health responses must take into consideration the local context, by considering the observed mortality risks among different socio-economic categories, such as sex (women vs men), age (younger vs older), and socioeconomic status (e.g., educational level or marital status conditions) (24). This study demonstrated the need to structure simultaneous cold and heat assessments within urban areas, with the objective to assess - on a local base - whether policies during colder periods are also needed in more temperate countries, beside those focusing only on summer. Finally, although the results of this study suggested a general increase of the mortality risk for each analysed subgroup, specific drivers of such a change still need to be identified. For this reason, it is necessary to maintain a continuous and updated research and local management approach.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thanks to Vijendra Ingole (KAUST University) for the continuous support in the research. I would like to thank Elisa Ferracin (ASL TO3) for the support to provide the initial mortality data. JB and HA gratefully acknowledge funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n. 865564 (European Research Council Consolidator Grant EARLY-ADAPT). JB gratefully acknowledges funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements n. 727852 (project Blue-Action) and n. 956396 (project EDIPI), and from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIU) under grant agreements n. RYC2018-025446-I (programme Ramón y Cajal) and EUR2019-103822 (project EURO-ADAPT). JR gratefully acknowledges funding from the EU Community Action Program for Public Health (grant agreement no 2005114). ISGlobal acknowledges support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation through the Centro de Excelencia Severo Ochoa 2019–2023 Program (CEX2018-000806-S) and support from the Generalitat de Catalunya through the CERCA programme.

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